

ISic0841

I.Sicily inscription 0841

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

cippus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

03.10.13

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 12

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Δεκομία
2. Συρίσκα
3. πανδόκια
4. χρηστὰ
5. χάρε

Apparatus

Text of IG

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492469

EDCS 39101995

PHI 140318

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0024 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Cagnat, R., Toutain, J., Jouguet, P. 1906-1927. Inscriptiones Graecae ad res Romanas pertinentes. Paris. At 493

Libertini, G 1929. Il regio museo archeologico di Siracusa. *Guide dei musei italiani.* Roma. At 121

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